

PREVENTIVE REGISTRATION AS A CRUCIAL MEASURE FOR INDIVIDUAL CRIME PREVENTION

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Abstract: This article analyzes the opinions of legal scholars and relevant legislative acts regarding preventive registration as an important measure for individual crime prevention. The author has developed proposals and recommendations based on this analysis.

Keywords: preventive registration, offenses, individual prevention, convicted persons.

Crime prevention has become one of the most pressing issues of our time. Especially today, with the changing social and economic conditions, the development of technologies and the impact of globalization, the types of offenses and the risks associated with them have increased. Therefore, measures in the field of early warning and prevention of offenses play an important role in ensuring the stability and security of society.

Article 35 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Prevention of Offenses" [1] defines the procedure for preventive accounting as one of the measures of individual crime prevention. This Article, through legal analysis, clearly determines which persons can be taken into preventive account. This article analyzes the significance and effectiveness of preventive accounting based on the current legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as international experience.

According to Article 35 of the law, preventive registration is carried out in relation to previously convicted persons after they have served a criminal sentence, except for persons against whom administrative control has been established, persons against whom a guilty verdict of the court has not been imposed, persons against whom a criminal case has been terminated or a decision to refuse to initiate a criminal case has been issued on non-rehabilitation grounds without resolving the issue of guilt in accordance with Article 84 of the Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, accused of committing a crime not related to

In our opinion, among the aforementioned individuals, previously convicted individuals are particularly important in preventive registration. Because previously convicted individuals form a group with a high probability of returning to criminal activity. This is also emphasized by many criminologists in their works.[2] After all, the fact that they have a criminal record shows that they have their own psychological and social characteristics. Such persons may pose a potential threat to public safety, especially if they are not fully rehabilitated from their criminal consequences.

Preventive registration of previously convicted persons is carried out in order to monitor and assist in the process of their return to society. This is aimed at preventing them from committing crimes again. Also, previously convicted individuals often face difficulties in adapting to social norms, as their criminal histories can create barriers to creating new opportunities for them. Therefore, it is important to develop rehabilitation and social

adaptation programs for them through preventive accounting, facilitating the process of their return to society.

At the same time, previously convicted individuals often face negative self-perception and stigma in society. All of these situations can lead to even more serious social and psychological problems for them. The system of preventive accounting serves as an important tool in supporting the process of social integration and recovery for these individuals. This will contribute to a decrease in the number of offenses in society, as well as the successful integration of previously convicted prisoners into the social system.

Therefore, the preventive registration of previously convicted persons is aimed not only at preventing offenses, but also at ensuring their return to a healthy and socially responsible lifestyle. Such an approach plays an extremely important role in ensuring stability and security in society.

The study of the practice of some foreign countries in this field leads to the following conclusions:

In particular, the US has a "parole" system as part of the supervision of previously convicted prisoners. The parole system aims to monitor convicted individuals for a certain period of time and ensure their social integration. Individuals who have been paroled will be under supervision for a certain period of time and will be provided with psychological support, vocational training, and other rehabilitation programs. This system has been shown to be effective in preventing previously convicted persons from committing repeat offenses.[3]

In Germany, previously convicted persons are provided with assistance through "economic rehabilitation" and "social services" to prevent recidivism. This will create opportunities for vocational training, psychological support, and finding their place in society for previously convicted prisoners, reducing the likelihood of their re-offending. In Germany, special attention is also paid to the development of self-management skills of previously convicted persons in preventive accounting.[4]

In some Scandinavian countries, re-socialization and rehabilitation of previously convicted persons is aimed at helping them in society and preventing them from committing crimes again. This system provides training, vocational training, and social adaptation programs for previously convicted persons. The system of preventive accounting in these countries is aimed not only at preventing crime, but also at the social rehabilitation of individuals who have returned to society.[5]

In England and Wales, a special "rehabilitation procedure" has been developed for previously convicted persons. In this system, there are several rehabilitation courses for previously convicted persons, each of which is adapted to the needs of the individual. This process significantly reduces the likelihood of repeat offenses by previously convicted individuals. There is also a system of oversight, where those previously convicted are under constant supervision after their return to the community.[6]

In conclusion, it can be said that preventive registration of previously convicted persons is an important tool for preventing their re-offending and ensuring their successful return to society. Scientific research and foreign experience show that preventive accounting should include not only control but also rehabilitation and social integration programs. These systems help previously convicted individuals adapt to society and reduce the likelihood of

repeat offenses. In the experience of Uzbekistan, the implementation of these approaches plays an important role in ensuring security in society.

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